

Antimicrobial results of two different doping concentrations of CNT with ZnO

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Abstract

CNT is doped with Zinc source material of Zinc acetate by using hydrothermal synthesis. The prepared materials with two different proportions was analysed as XRD and SEM with EDAX using sophisticated instrument to confirm expected elements present with strong bond by evaluating and serious care on diffraction peaks which becomes sharper, surface morphology and energy dispersive amplitude. From the analysis of XRD, we found that all the crystal phases are anatase formation and there is a characteristic peak of ZnO at 2θ values which matches with JCPDS 36-1451 and JCPDS 26-1079 which is corresponding to CNT. TEM and SAED investigated the entitled compound that particles size, shape and presence of oxygen under Zn and CNT remand. The successful expected result has been obtained and explained after its serious analyzing antibacterial research stations that announcing the great attention for ability of bacterial inhibition.

Key words: ZnO-CNT, SEM, EDAX and Antibacterial.

References

- [1] Caihong Wang et al., Sensors and Actuators B, 113 (2006) 320–323.
- [2] Chu Xiangfeng et al., Chemical Physics Letters, 401 (2005) 426–429.
- [3] H. T. Wang et al., Applied Physics Letters, 86 (2005) 243503.